
**A STUDY ON CONSUMER AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION OF
AYURVEDIC PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO
COIMBATORE CITY**

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Abstract:

This study focused on consumer awareness and perception of ayurvedic products with special reference to Coimbatore city. Convenience sample method is used to collect the data from the respondents. The sampling size of the responding is 100. Percentage analysis is used to analysis the collected data. After an analysis of response received, it has been concluded that people of Coimbatore city are well aware of Ayurvedic products. The consumer have good opinion about Ayurvedic products.

Introduction:

'Ayurveda' is the 'science of life'. Since life is synonymous with health, Ayurveda is deemed to be the 'science of human health'. Ayurveda's approach towards healing is holistic. It doesn't deal with individual organs in isolation, but treats the body as a whole. More important, it doesn't give temporary relief, but cure the disease.

Ayurvedic medicine, as practiced in India, is one of the oldest systems of medicine in the world. Many Ayurvedic

practices predate written records and were handed down by word of mouth. Two ancient books, written in Sanskrit more than 2,000 years ago, are considered the main texts on Ayurvedic medicine—Caraka Samhita and Sushruta Samhita.

It gives emphasis to the triune nature of each person: body care, mental regulation, and spiritual/consciousness refinement. Ayurvedic medicine continues to be practiced in India, where nearly 80 percent of the population uses it exclusively or combined with conventional

(Western) medicine. It is also practiced in Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Nepal, and Pakistan. Most major cities in India have an Ayurvedic college & hospitals. The Indian government began systematic research on Ayurvedic practices in 1969, and that work continues.

The success of the business firms significantly depends upon the consumer's preference. It's important to track this factor and work on improving it in order to make your customers more loyal and eventually turn them into brand representatives. Customer preferences are expectations, likes, and dislikes, motivations and preferences that drive customers purchasing decision. It's defined as the way that consumers usually view or feel about certain products and services. Customer preference of individual consumer's utility. Consumer value can be determined by how consumers are not contained within the fields of economics. These customer preferences are dictated by personal taste, culture, education and many other factors such as social pressure from friends and phone because her friends all have the same brand. It's also can be related to customer preference which is the probability of consumers towards the Ayurvedic products.

Objectives:

1. To study the consumer awareness

towards Ayurvedic products

2. To study about the consumer satisfaction on Ayurvedic products
3. To identify the problems faced by the consumer by using Ayurvedic products.
4. To analyse the factors influencing brand preference on Ayurvedic products

Statement of Problem:

Ayurvedic products are manufacture from natural ingredients. Due to industrialization and deforestation, there is no space for the growth of Ayurvedic raw materials i.e, (plant parts). Expecting speedy results people prefer allopathy irrespective of its side effects, which leads to decrease in customer preference towards Ayurvedic products. Hence this research aims is to explore the customers preference towards selected Ayurvedic products.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

A research design is the set of methods and procedures used in collecting and analysis measure of the variables specified in research problems. The research design is the conceptual structure which represents is conducted. It constitutes the blue print for collections, measurement an analysis of data. The

design used for carrying this research is Exploratory.

Sampling Method:

To get the information about the topic from the consumers convenience sample method is used. Under this have prepared a simple questionnaire to collect the information.

Sampling Size:

The study was conducted towards Ayurvedic product users. The size of the responding is 100.

Area of Research:

The area of research is conducted in Coimbatore City.

Source of Data:

For this study both primary and secondary data were used.

Statistical Tools:

The statistical methods involved in carrying out a study include collecting data, analysing, interpretation and reporting of the research findings.

- Percentage Analysis and
- Ranking method are used.

Indhumathy (2019), "A study on customer preference towards Dabur products in Salem town". The focus of this project is to increase the consumption of Dabur products and help the organization from constant threat from its competitors and suggest the ways and opportunities to

maintain the share of Dabur products. To study the effect of various factor on the purchase of Dabur products like price, quality awareness. And also, examine the behaviour of the consumer gender wise and age wise. Ayurvedic products are reasonable cost effective and well accepted by customers. They are easily available and do not have side effects. Dabur enjoying the profitable position in market through spirituality element involved unit's products. So, it is up to the players in the market to provide multiple options and at the same time maintain a perfect balance between the quality and price of the personal care products.

Dr. A. Radhakrishnan and Radhika, K (2018), "A study on customer satisfaction Towards Himalaya products with reference to Cuddalore town" In this study customer satisfaction is defined as the "the number of customers, or percentage of total customers, whose exported experience with a firm, its products, or is services exceeds specified satisfaction is seen as a key differentiator and increasingly has become a key element of business strategy. To ascertain customer requirements of Himalaya skin care products and identify the problem faced by the respondents while using Himalaya products. Customer is influenced by their attitude towards the product and therefore marketers need to product to implement

their strategies and tactics frequently in order to achieve more consumers. It gives good result to the users because each of the Himalayas are researched and trailed by the research and development centre of Himalaya Company. So, the producer should understand what is exactly expected from him by the consumers facilitated to increase its sale as much.

Suganya. Rand Dr. Hamsalakshmi R (2017). "A study on customer buying behaviour of selected Ayurvedic healthcare products. The customer satisfaction for a product depends upon a number of aspects like price and quality are of the prime importance. This study aims to find the customer preference and level of satisfaction on Ayurvedic healthcare products and to identify the factors influencing their preference. In this research, it is found that respondents prefer a specific brand because of the chemical free product and quality of the products. The customer buying a variety of Ayurvedic healthcare products which satisfy his wants and they are always influenced by his purchasing activities by some considerations which lead him to select a particular brand or a particular store in preferred to others.

Dr. Ramakrishna Bhandaru (2017)", "The study examines the usage of consumer towards Ayurvedic products compare to the other products available in

the market The data collection was conducted in the city of Hyderabad. As per the findings of the researcher consumer are more preferable towards the Ayurvedic products they feel very convenient in the intension of better health in Indian food market. Irrespective of "Swadesh or Videsh" products all categories of customers have preferred the Ayurvedic in Hyderabad city. Ayurvedic and natural food products are going to occupy major share and becoming a leader in Indian food market.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Awareness about the Ayurvedic Products

	Respondents	Percentage
Media	28	28%
Relatives	41	41%
Friends	21	21%
Families	10	10%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

The above table states that majority 41% of the respondents belongs to relatives, 28% of the respondents belongs to media, and 21% of the respondents belong to friends, and 10% of the respondents belong to families.

Preference Brand of the Ayurvedic Products

Brand	Respondents	Percentage
Himalayan	42	42%
Lever Ayuth	14	14%
Medimix	25	25%
Pathanjli	07	07%
Dabur	05	05%
Others	07	07%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

The above table states that majority 42% of the respondents says they are aware of Himalayan products, 25% of the respondents says medimix, 14% of the respondents says lever ayuth, 7% of the respondents says Patanjali and others ayurvedic products, and 5% of the respondents says Dabur.

Satisfaction Level of Ayurvedic Product

Satisfaction	Respondents	Percentage
Very High	32	32%
High	37	37%
Neutral	27	27%
Low	04	04%
Very Low	0	0%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

The above table states that majority 37% of the respondents says highly satisfy on ayurvedic products, 32% of the respondents says very highly satisfy, 27% of the respondents says neutral, 4% of the

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respondents says low and no respondents says very low.

Overall Quality of Ayurvedic Product

Satisfaction	Respondents	Percentage
Very Poor	01	01%
Poor	03	03%
Average	24	24%
Good	40	40%
Very Good	32	32%
Total	100	100%

Source: Primary data

Interpretation:

The above table states that majority 40% of the respondents says good on ayurvedic products, 32% of the respondents says very highly satisfy, 27% of the respondents says neutral, 4% of the respondents says low and no respondents says very low.

Findings:

- Majority 73% of the respondent are male.
- Majority 68% of the respondent are female between 20 – 30.
- Majority 65% of the respondent are Under graduation.
- Majority 59% of the respondent are student.
- Majority 61% of the respondent are unmarried.
- Majority 66 % of the respondent are 3-5 family members.
- Majority 42% of the respondents belongs to 10000-20000 income.

- Majority 93% responds says yes they are aware on ayurvedic products.
- Majority 41% of the respondents belongs to relatives.
- Majority 33% of the respondents says, buy of ayurvedic products weakly.
- Majority 48% of the respondents says that the price of ayurvedic product is average.
- Majority 42% of the respondents says they are aware of Himalayan products.
- Majority 63% of the respondents says that no that the ayurvedic products did not cause side effect on our body.
- Majority 43% of the respondents says Medi mix soap.
- Majority 38% of the respondents says Indhulekha shampoo.
- Majority 51% of the respondents says Indhulekha bringha oil.
- Majority 37% of the respondents says Colgate Swarna vedshakti toothpaste.
- Majority 37% of the respondents says highly satisfy on ayurvedic products.
- Majority 40% of the respondents says good on ayurvedic products.
- Majority 93% of the respondents says yes they will recommend the ayurvedic product to their friends & family.
- Majority 77% of the respondents says health conditions of using ayurvedic product is good.

- Majority 90% of the respondents says yes that the respondents like to buy ayurvedic products again.

Suggestion:

- The Ayurvedic brands should focus more on redesigning the present products by investing more in research and design.
- The commercial ads by the Ayurvedic brands should try to feature face of film stars, sports person etc in order to build a positive image in the minds of the customers
- Government should take necessary steps to improve the sales of ayurvedic by giving due important to quality, sales effort etc
- Through proper channel awareness can be enhanced.
- Increase the Ayurvedic shop.
- Majority of the respondents feel that the product quality is good. So the Ayurvedic Company can try maintaining the same level quality.

Conclusion:

The study reveals that Ayurvedic industry undergone systematic transaction over the years. After an analysis of response received, it has been concluded that people of Coimbatore city are well aware of Ayurvedic products. The primary concern is to cope up with the customers by focusing on natural and nutrition advice. The consumer have good opinion about Ayurvedic products. The result of the study are useful in managerial decision making as

they give useful insights of customer preference of Ayurvedic products.

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